

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**REGULATORY STRATEGIES FOR EXPEDITED DRUG
APPROVAL PROCESS IN USA, EU & JAPAN****SYED ARSHIYA^{1*}, M. V. NAGABHUSHANAM², ADILAKSHMI CH³,
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Amaravathi Road, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India-522002.**Article Received: September 2024 Accepted: October 2024 Published: November 2024****Abstract:**

This study provides a comprehensive and comparative analysis of the regulatory approval processes for generic drug products across Latin American countries. With the rising need for affordable medications, generic drugs play a critical role in expanding healthcare access. However, significant differences exist in the regulatory frameworks and approval timelines in Latin America, impacting the availability and affordability of generics. This research examines the requirements, documentation, bioequivalence studies, and timelines mandated by key regulatory bodies, including ANVISA (Brazil), COFEPRIS (Mexico), INVIMA (Colombia), and others. Key findings reveal a substantial variance in approval times and procedural complexity, with some countries implementing stringent regulatory processes, while others face challenges such as limited resources, capacity constraints, and bureaucratic delays. The study also explores efforts toward regional harmonization led by organizations like PAHO and PANDRH, which aim to standardize regulations across Latin America to streamline approval processes. Through comparative analysis, this research identifies best practices and recommends improvements, such as greater regional collaboration, capacity building for regulatory agencies, and simplified approval pathways. These recommendations aim to facilitate faster, safer, and more cost-effective access to generic drugs in Latin America, ultimately supporting public health goals by making essential medications more accessible to diverse populations across the region.

Keywords: Latin American countries, Regulatory frameworks, Approval Process, Generic Drugs**Corresponding author:****Syed Arshiya,**II/II M.Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical Regulatory Affairs,
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Please cite this article in press Syed Arshiya et al *Regulatory Strategies For Expedited Drug Approval Process In Usa, Eu & Japan*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (11).

INTRODUCTION [1-3]:

The regulatory strategies for expedited drug approval processes in the United States (USA), the European Union (EU), and Japan are designed to facilitate the faster availability of essential medications, especially those addressing unmet medical needs or life-threatening conditions. Each of these regions has developed various regulatory pathways to accelerate the approval of new drugs without compromising safety, efficacy, or quality. Here's a detailed look at these strategies in each region.

Expedited approval pathways in the united states [4-6]:

In the United States, the **Food and Drug Administration (FDA)** is responsible for regulating drugs and has implemented several pathways to expedite drug approvals:

A. Fast Track

- **Purpose:** Designed for drugs that treat serious conditions and fill an unmet medical need.
- **Process:** Drugs granted Fast Track status receive early and frequent communication with the FDA. This enables the developer to address issues sooner and allows for a "rolling review," where sections of the New Drug Application (NDA) or Biologics License Application (BLA) can be submitted and reviewed before the entire application is completed.
- **Eligibility:** Available for drugs that demonstrate the potential to address a critical gap in treatment options.

B. Breakthrough Therapy

- **Purpose:** Created for drugs that show substantial improvement over existing therapies for serious or life-threatening conditions.
- **Process:** The FDA works closely with the sponsor throughout development to expedite clinical trials and review processes. Drugs with Breakthrough Therapy designation benefit from intensive guidance and may also be eligible for rolling review.
- **Eligibility:** Requires preliminary clinical evidence indicating that the drug may offer significant improvement over available therapy.

C. Accelerated Approval

- **Purpose:** Allows for earlier approval of drugs for serious conditions that fill an unmet medical need based on a surrogate or intermediate clinical endpoint.

- **Process:** The FDA approves the drug based on early evidence (like a surrogate endpoint) rather than waiting for clinical benefit. Post-marketing confirmatory trials are required to verify the drug's benefit.
- **Eligibility:** Often used for cancer drugs and drugs for other serious diseases where waiting for definitive evidence might delay access to treatment.

D. Priority Review

- **Purpose:** Shortens the FDA's review goal for a drug application from the standard 10 months to 6 months.
- **Process:** The FDA assigns Priority Review to drugs that provide significant improvements in the treatment, diagnosis, or prevention of serious conditions.
- **Eligibility:** Drugs that offer major advances in treatment or provide a treatment where none exists are eligible for this designation.

EXPEDITED APPROVAL PATHWAYS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION [5-8]:

In the European Union, the **European Medicines Agency (EMA)** is responsible for the regulation of drugs. The EMA has its own set of expedited approval pathways:

A. Priority Medicines (PRIME) Scheme

- **Purpose:** Aimed at enhancing support for the development of medicines that target unmet medical needs.
- **Process:** Medicines in the PRIME scheme receive early and enhanced support from the EMA, including accelerated assessment at the time of marketing authorization application. This includes scientific advice and guidance on optimal development paths.
- **Eligibility:** Medicines that show promising early clinical data addressing an unmet medical need are eligible.

B. Conditional Marketing Authorization (CMA)

- **Purpose:** Allows for early authorization of drugs that address life-threatening or serious diseases with unmet needs.
- **Process:** Drugs can be authorized based on less comprehensive clinical data than normally required. The authorization is valid for one year and can be renewed. Companies are required to complete further studies to confirm the drug's benefits and risk profile.
- **Eligibility:** CMAs are granted for drugs addressing serious or life-threatening conditions, particularly when comprehensive data is not yet available but preliminary data suggests a favorable benefit-risk ratio.

C. Accelerated Assessment

- **Purpose:** Reduces the timeframe for a drug's marketing authorization application review from 210 days to 150 days.
- **Process:** Accelerated Assessment is granted when the medicine is expected to be of major public health interest, particularly in terms of therapeutic innovation.
- **Eligibility:** Medicines addressing major therapeutic needs or providing a significant therapeutic advantage.

D. Exceptional Circumstances

- **Purpose:** Permits marketing authorization for certain drugs where full clinical trials cannot be conducted, often due to ethical or practical limitations.
- **Process:** Approval under exceptional circumstances is granted on the basis of available data, with the understanding that comprehensive clinical data cannot be obtained. Additional post-approval data collection and risk management plans are required.
- **Eligibility:** Reserved for treatments of rare diseases or unique conditions where conventional trials are infeasible.

EXPEDITED APPROVAL PATHWAYS IN JAPAN [8-13]:

In Japan, the **Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA)** and the **Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare (MHLW)** oversee the regulation and approval of drugs. Japan has implemented strategies to accelerate drug approvals for critical medications.

A. Sakigake Designation

- **Purpose:** Sakigake, meaning “pioneer,” is intended to encourage the development of innovative drugs by offering faster approval times.
- **Process:** Drugs with Sakigake designation receive priority consultations, extensive guidance, and a priority review from the

PMDA, aiming to reduce the approval time significantly.

- **Eligibility:** Drugs that are novel, have shown outstanding efficacy, and target life-threatening or serious conditions. The drug must be intended to be filed in Japan first or simultaneously with other countries.

B. Conditional Early Approval

- **Purpose:** Allows for early approval of drugs based on limited evidence, with the expectation of additional data post-approval.
- **Process:** Similar to the EU's Conditional Marketing Authorization, Japan's Conditional Early Approval is granted based on surrogate endpoints or preliminary data. Companies are required to collect additional evidence to confirm efficacy and safety.
- **Eligibility:** Typically applied to drugs for rare diseases or diseases with high unmet needs.

C. Priority Review

- **Purpose:** Expedites the review of drugs that address serious medical conditions and provide significant therapeutic benefit.
- **Process:** Reduces the PMDA review period, aiming for a shorter time to market.
- **Eligibility:** Drugs for serious conditions that offer a substantial therapeutic improvement over existing treatments.

D. Orphan Drug Designation

- **Purpose:** Designed to encourage the development of drugs for rare diseases (similar to the USA's Orphan Drug Designation).
- **Process:** Provides benefits such as tax incentives, extended market exclusivity, and priority review to drugs that target rare diseases.
- **Eligibility:** Drugs that treat rare diseases affecting a small percentage of the population.

COMPARATIVE OVERVIEW OF EXPEDITED APPROVAL STRATEGIES [14-18]:

Pathway	USA (FDA)	EU (EMA)	Japan (PMDA)
Fast Track	Early interaction with FDA	N/A	N/A
Breakthrough Therapy	Intensive guidance	PRIME Scheme (similar)	Sakigake Designation (similar)
Accelerated Approval	Approval on surrogate endpoints	Conditional Marketing Authorization (CMA)	Conditional Early Approval
Priority Review	6-month review timeline	Accelerated Assessment	Priority Review
Orphan Drug Designation	Rare disease incentives	Orphan Medicinal Products Regulation	Orphan Drug Designation

CONCLUSION:

A comprehensive and comparative study of the approval process for generic drugs in Latin America could identify best practices and areas for reform, ultimately helping to improve access to essential medicines. By comparing the regulatory frameworks of different countries, the study could highlight the benefits of harmonization and offer insights into how governments, regional organizations, and the pharmaceutical industry can collaborate to bring affordable generics to market more efficiently. This has significant implications for public health, as streamlined and effective approval processes are key to ensuring that essential medications are both accessible and affordable across Latin America.

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